

Plasmon Controlled Shaping of Gold Nanoparticle Aggregates by Femtosecond Laser Induced Melting[†]

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Abstract

In this work we show how to control the morphology of femtosecond laser melted gold nanosphere aggregates. A careful choice of both laser fluence and wavelength

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makes it possible to selectively excite different aggregate substructures to produce larger spherical nanoparticles, nanorods and nanoprisms or necklace-like 1D nanostructures in which the nanoparticles are interlinked by bridges. Finite integral technique calculations have been performed on the near-field concentration of light in the nanostructures which confirm the wavelength dependence of the light concentration and suggest that the resulting localised high intensities can lead to non-thermal melting. In particular, we demonstrate that by tuning the wavelength of the melting light it is possible to match different plasmonic/interband frequencies and thus the spatial extension of the ensembles of NPs heated allowing us to exhibit control over the morphology of the nanostructures formed by the melting process. The combination of this wavelength controlled melting with the self-assembly of nanoparticles on surfaces could find applications in nanofabrication techniques.

Keywords

Thermoplasmonics, Nanomelting, Nanofabrication

The interaction of visible light with gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) and nanostructures has been the subject of intensive study in recent decades.^{1,2} Much of this interest has been stimulated by the presence of the localised surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) of AuNPs in the visible range arising due to a resonance between the oscillating dipole created by displaced electrons in the NPs and the light field impinging on the NPs. Furthermore, the photon confinement induced by the LSPR strongly enhances all radiative and non-radiative processes in the vicinity of the surface of the particles. This has led to a myriad of applications of AuNPs.³ One of the most attractive features of these structures is the possibility to deposit heat in a controlled manner on the nanoscale.^{4,5} This localised heating has been exploited in a number of applications such as photothermal therapy⁶⁻¹⁰ and photocatalysis.¹¹

Furthermore, the irradiation of nanoparticles with light can be used to control their morphology either by guiding wet synthesis paths,^{12,13} direct reshaping of the nanoparticles by

melting¹⁴⁻²⁰ or nanowelding.²¹⁻²⁵ For example, techniques have been developed which involve low intensity light to interact with certain plasmon frequencies of chemically fabricated triangular nanoplates thus inhibiting their growth and fusion and exerting control over the final morphology of the synthesis products.^{12,13} Another interesting example of using light to control morphology is the recent work of González-Rubio *et al.*²⁰ which showed that it is possible to reshape an ensemble of Au nanorods with light in order to achieve aspect ratio dispersity as low as 2%. More directly related to the work presented here is the technique of light induced nanowelding which already some years ago was used to weld Au/Ag nanoparticles in aggregates^{22,26} and Ag nanowires²⁵ to each other. Recently some notable refinements of the technique have been made in which light has been used to "thread" strings of NPs together²⁷ as well as to weld gold nanorods tip-to-tip in a controlled manner¹⁸ in some cases achieving sub-nanometer resolution on the final morphology of the welded NPs. In spite of the extensive research in this area the precise mechanisms of the above processes are not fully understood. This is due to the complex interplay of a large number of factors such as the length of the melting light pulse, the effect of hot spots due to the nanoantenna effect in metal nanostructures, different regimes where absorption or near field effects dominate, thermal vs. non-thermal melting, local vs. isotropic melting, plasma generation and non-linear effects (REFS). A full understanding of these factors together with accurately controlled self-assembly of nanoparticles on surfaces would lead to a nanofabrication technique with unprecedented spatial resolution and processing speeds by combining the advantages of top-down and bottom-up techniques.²⁸

In this letter we propose the use of tunable femtosecond laser radiation to induce the melting of nanoparticle aggregates into nanostructures with controlled size and shape, by tuning the wavelength of the melting radiation to coincide with different types of plasmonic and/or interband heating of the NPs. In particular, self-assembled aggregates of AuNPs stabilized by Isothiocyanate Rhodamine B (RITC) in water solutions have been subject to melting and the nanostructures produced have been characterized by static and transient

Three beam experiment

Figure 1: Schematics of the experimental setup employed for the melting and spectroscopic diagnostics of the AgNP aggregate solutions. Figure needs to be greatly improved. This one is just copied from the internet. My attempts with POVray have not been successful.

absorption spectroscopy (TAS) and electron microscopy measurements.

In a previous publication,²⁹ we characterized the structure and the spectroscopic behaviour of the investigated aggregates, and demonstrated how their plasmonic response could be controlled by varying the quantity of RITC molecules on the surface of the AuNPs.

The comparison between a model calculation and the experimental static absorbance data revealed that the data were best reproduced by a model involving chains of 10 nm diameter gold nanoparticles of various lengths separated by 1 nm with the interparticle region best described by the dielectric constant of water. These results agree with previous studies which showed that the plasmonic response of the aggregates are controlled to produce a broad spatially extended plasmon resonance due to delocalization of the plasmon resonance over a number of particles.^{30,31} It has been shown that small shifts of the plasmon resonance corresponds to delocalization of the resonance over few NPs while larger shifts are correspond to more delocalized resonances (for a given interparticle distance).³⁰⁻³²

Here, we have used the plasmonic response of the nanoparticle aggregates as a tool to induce selective melting of aggregates with different spatial extents, by using a 3 beam set-up (see Figure 1): namely a melting, a pump and a probe beam. The melting beam is first used to irradiate the sample and induce melting of the AuNPs aggregates. This melting beam is then blocked and the pump and probe beams are delivered to the same spot to record the transient absorption spectrum of the melted sample. When the pump and probe beams are focussed to the same spot where the melting laser has changed the morphology of the NP aggregates in solution it is possible to locally characterise the effect of the melting laser before diffusion disperses the melted structures. The temporal delay between the low power pump (400 nm, $50 \mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$) and the white light probe (350-800 nm) is set to a single value (1 ps) so that the transient spectra can be acquired in a few seconds. More details on the laser system and on the pump-probe geometry are provided in the supporting information. This *in-situ* spectroscopic diagnostic procedure allows us to characterise the effect of the laser fluence and wavelength of the melting beam on the nanostructures produced. The above procedure allowed us to set the laser fluence of the melting beam so as to deplete the desired part of the spectral response of the aggregates within seconds while avoiding too low power levels where the nanoparticles are able to dissipate all of the heat of the pump laser without morphological changes or too high powers where the plasmonic response (particularly the extended plasmon) is completely depleted due, for example, to nanocavitation and/or precipitation of the nanostructures.² The three wavelengths chosen for the melting laser were 400 nm which corresponds mainly to interband excitation, 570 nm which corresponds to center of the transverse plasmon resonance and 620 to the maximum of the extended longitudinal plasmon resonance. The power densities chosen for these melting wavelengths were $7.0 \times 10^{10} \text{ W}/\text{cm}^2$, $2.5 \times 10^{10} \text{ W}/\text{cm}^2$ and $2.5 \times 10^{10} \text{ W}/\text{cm}^2$, for 400 nm, 570 nm and 650 nm, respectively.

In order to produce a macroscopic quantity of melted aggregates for further analysis the cuvette containing the solution was rastered over the laser spot until the entire solution (100

Figure 2: (a) Static and (b) transient absorbances of non-irradiated sample and the samples irradiated at 400, 570 and 620 nm. (c) Photograph of the irradiated samples.

μl) had been irradiated for the same amount of time (5- 10 sec). The result was a change in colour of the entire solutions due to the morphological changes brought on by the irradiation (see Figure 2 (c) for a photograph of the irradiated samples). The spectroscopic evidence shows the progressive depletion of the extended plasmon resonance on going from 620 to 570 nm with a shift of the resonance to the blue occurring for irradiation with 400 nm. We interpret these observations in the following manner: the plasmonic heating (570, 620) leads to a preferential melting of different structures within the aggregates with the 570 nm being mainly absorbed by small structures while the red light is mainly absorbed by long chain-like or 2-D structures. These effects are even clearer in the transient absorption spectra due to the narrower plasmonic features (see Figure 2 (b)). This is similar to what is observed in

the case of the welding of strings of particles AuNP where the extended plasmon feature in the separated particles in the visible is strongly red-shifted when the particles are threaded together thus producing a longitudinal plasmon resonance in the near-IR.²⁷

The 400 nm melting exhibits different spectroscopic markers with respect to the plasmonically heated samples showing a shift of the plasmon resonance to higher energy. This can be interpreted as being due to destruction of the aggregates and formation of isolated particles characterised by the typical spherical AuNP plasmon resonance in water at 520 nm.³³

Figure 3: Size distributions of spherical particles (histogram) and lognormal fit (solid line) of the non-irradiated sample (a), and samples irradiated at 400 nm (b), 570 nm (c) and 620 nm (d), with the fitting parameter $x_c = 9.6, 11.5, 10.2$ and 9.3 , respectively. Measurements are extracted from a series of SEM images.

We have analysed the size distribution of spherical particles contained in the melted samples by performing electron microscopy measurements. To perform the SEM measurements

the dispersions of Au-RITC in water are sonicated in order to assure good dispersion, deposited by casting on a monocrystalline silicon wafer and dried in standard conditions. The samples prepared in this way were investigated through SEM analysis using a Field Emission SEM Zeiss Auriga 405. The size distribution of the untreated sample and that of the 400 nm treated samples are shown in Figures 3 (a) and (b), respectively. Comparison of the two size distributions clearly shows that the melting has led to the formation of larger spherical NPs with a shift of the maximum of the log-norm fit of the size distribution from 9.6 to 11.5 nm. The appearance of these larger particles can be observed in the SEM image shown in Figure 4 (b) where there is also an illustration of the proposed melting mechanism, the details of which will be discussed further on in the text. In contrast, melting at 570 and 620 nm do not result in significant changes in the size distributions of the spherical particles (see Figures 3 (c) and (d)).

Apart from the change of the size distribution further examination of the SEM images of the samples melted with 570 and 650 nm light revealed the appearance of some new particle shapes which were not present in the original samples. Indeed, melting/irradiation of the sample at 570 nm has quite a different effect with respect to the heating at 400 nm. This is testified by the appearance of a number triangular and rod shaped particles which were not present in the untreated samples (see Figures 4 (c)). The yield of this process is quite low although this is not surprising considering the small changes in the static absorbances after the melting. Only a small subset of the aggregate geometries undergo melting. The illustrations in panel (c) of Figure 4 show the processes we suggest must take place to produce such particle shapes and involve the fusion of dimers and trimers. These particles are not simply due to the formation of bridges between particles but rather the complete melting of particles and formation of new shapes. This may be due to the combined effects of heating through the transverse and extended plasmon resonances. Finally, heating on the red side of the extended plasmon resonance leads to the formation of larger structures (see Figure 4 (d)) which are due to threading/melting of longer 1D chains and 2D arrays

Figure 4: SEM images of AuNP aggregates (a) not irradiated and after irradiation with (b) 400 nm, (c) 570 nm (d) 620 nm laser light. Illustrations of the proposed mechanism of how the melting takes place following irradiation at 400 nm, 570 nm and at 620 nm are shown as insets in the corresponding panels. Colored ovals on the SEM images highlight particular shapes formed in the melting. White bars of length 100 nm are shown on each of the SEM images. Will try to add "sparks" to the melting structures to illustrate the hot spots.

of the NP aggregate. This is, in some respects, similar (at least in the 1D case) to the effects achieved in Herrmann *et al.*²⁷. The difference here is that we have shown that by a combination of plasmon control of the AuNP starting aggregate and selective excitation of different parts of the plasmon resonance it is possible to select the shapes and types of nanostructures formed in the melting process.

As mentioned above there are many factors to be taken into account when considering the mechanism of melting including different laser fluences, the environment of the NPs, hot spots, plasma generation,^{34,35} non-linear processes,³⁶⁻³⁸ non-thermal effects^{34,35} and the interplay between these aspects. However before considering in detail the melting process and

proposing a mechanism it is useful to briefly review the dissipation of heat by gold NPs at low pump fluences. For isolated NPs at laser fluences $< 10^{10}$ W/cm² (500 μ J/cm² for a 50 fs laser) the particles are capable of dissipating all of the heat generated by the absorbed light via the following sequence of events: absorption of light (during laser pulse), electron thermalisation via electron-electron scattering (up to several hundreds of femtoseconds), electron-phonon scattering allowing exchange of energy between the electrons and the lattice (< 10 ps) and, finally, phonon-phonon scattering (hundreds of ps) in which the NP dissipates the energy absorbed as heat to the environment.³³ Therefore the lattice temperature of the NPs returns to room temperature on the scale of hundred of picoseconds by phonon-phonon coupling between the Au lattice and the environment (capping molecules and water). Considering the above times scales and that fact that the time between laser pulses is 1 ms, then for melting to take place the lattice must reach the melting point after a single pulse as there is no possibility of the NPs to store heat from one shot to the next. At high fluences ($> 10^{12}$ W/cm²) one observes nanocavitation and explosive boiling of the water surrounding the NPs.³⁹ Between these extremes and sometimes at lower intensities it is possible to encounter intermediate cases where part or all of the NP melts, e.g. Petrova *et al.*⁴⁰ observed reshaping of nanorods with intensities in the range 1.0×10^9 - 2.6×10^{10} W/cm², while Herrmann *et al.*²⁷ observed threading of NPs already at 9.0×10^7 W/cm². The laser fluences used here are almost identical to those used by Petrova *et al.*⁴⁰ but more than two orders of magnitude larger than Herrmann *et al.*²⁷ Boulais *et al.*³⁴ suggested the existence of two regimes in the laser irradiation of nanorods in water: i) an absorption regime in which the Nps strongly absorb radiation and ii) a near field regime in which the energy transfer from the light field is dominated by the action of the hot-spots (created by the nanoantenna effect) in ionizing and heating the resulting nanoplasma in the surrounding water. Furthermore, they suggested a passage from the first to the second of these regimes at a fluence of 6.6×10^9 W/cm² which is comparable to the intensities used here. Also, Herrmann *et al.*²⁷ in their threading experiment showed that the melting depended on peak power and not average power and as

a result suggested that the melting was due to e-m hotspots weakening the lattice combined with enhanced optical forces acting on the mobile surface atoms drawing them into the gap. With respect to the fluences used in this work Herrmann *et al.*²⁷ used much lower values and yet achieved melting similar to that shown in Figure 4 (d). In any case it is clear from the above discussion that at intermediate laser fluences it is not possible to consider only the laser fluences/intensities without also taking into account the presence of hot-spots.

Numerous theoretical models of melting have been presented⁴¹⁻⁴⁶ however they are generally very dependent on the details of the melting and often do not completely take the effects of hot spots into account. Here in order to distinguish between isotropic thermal heating and anisotropic non-thermal heating we adopt the method suggested by Baffou *et al.*⁴⁷ This method assumes that all of the absorbed light is transformed into isotropic heating of the lattice of the NP. While this is not true it does give an upper limit to the temperature to be reached by isotropic thermal heating and can be calculated using the formula :

$$\Delta T_{max} = \frac{\sigma_{abs} F}{V \rho_{Au} C_{Au}} \quad (1)$$

where σ_{abs} is the absorption cross-section, F is the fluence of the laser, V is the volume of the NP, ρ_{Au} is the mass density of gold which has a value⁵ of 1.932×10^4 kg/m³ and C_{Au} is the specific heat capacity of gold which has a value⁵ of 129 J/kg/K. The calculation of σ_{abs} using Mie theory for a single gold NP of diameter 10 nm in water yields values of 27.0, 12.0 and 1.3 nm² for 400, 570 and 650 nm, respectively. These values lead to maximum temperature increases of the lattices 1313, 239 and 26 K respectively. In the first case of 400 nm it is clear that at the irradiation intensities used melting of individual NPs is possible while in the cases plasmonic heating at 570 and 650 nm this is not possible.

We therefore would like to evaluate if non-isotropic melting can occur in the case of plasmonic heating such that the heat is locally concentrated in parts of the aggregate. The obvious question to ask is what is the light field amplification due to concentration of light on the nanoscale by the nanoantenna effect. To answer this question we have performed FIT

calculations. FIT is a powerful numerical approach for solving electromagnetic problems, especially suitable for large dimension structures with detailed features. It was first introduced by Thomas Weiland in 1977.⁴⁸ It is based on the solution of the Maxwell equations in their integral form. The FIT method allows the calculation in both near- and far-field. In this work we concentrate on the electric-field distributions in the near fields to assess the spatial extension and location of the hot spots as well as the numerical extent of the amplification of the field. The results are shown in Figure 5 for 400 and 600 nm light illuminating 4 NPs of 10 nm diameter separated by 1 nm, embedded in water, with the electric field vector of the illuminating light aligned along the interparticle axis of the chain and the direction of propagation of the light perpendicular to this axis. *Need to explain this choice by reference to previous publication.*

Figure 5: Concentration of the light field (a) 400 nm and (b) 600 nm. *Will put E/E_0 instead of in V/m . Will also add the k and E vectors to the figures.*

Unsurprisingly one observes hot spots in the regions between the NPs. However, it is the value of the field enhancement, particularly in the case of the plasmonic excitation at

600 nm, which gives us an indication of the kind of mechanisms which may participate in the melting. Indeed, a local enhancement of almost 2 orders of magnitude of the field near the surfaces of the NPs facing the interparticle gap leads to a local field on the order of 10^{12} W/cm². In this intensity regime non-linear effects such as multiphoton absorption, plasma formation, impact ionisation of water, and attraction between NPs due to light trapping must be considered.

The additional information on the mechanisms which we can extract from the present work stems from the different type of melting processes which take place following the heating of the particles with different wavelengths of light. For 400 nm light the melting only stops when the aggregate is almost destroyed. This can be understood from the fact that the hot-spots are much less pronounced at 400 nm with respect to the plasmonic heating both in absolute intensity and in spatial localisation (see Figure 5 (a)) and so higher pump powers were employed ($\sim 10^{11}$ W/cm²). [Not sure that the last sentence is completely true considering the new calculations.](#) This leads to participation of more isotropic melting which leads to complete melting of the particles and formation of larger spherical particles as observed. Contemporary excitation of transverse and extended plasmon resonances (at 570 nm) where the extended resonance is delocalized only on few particles leads to melting in the hotspot regions of dimer and trimers. After the initial fusion the extended/logitudinal plasmon resonance will strongly shift to the red however the transverse plasmon will continue to be excited and may allow further melting to convert the particles into regular shapes (rods and triangular nanoplates). Finally, heating on the red side of the extended plasmon at 650 nm we get a similar mechanism to that proposed by Herrmann *et al.*²⁷ (in the case of 1D structures), i.e. non-thermal melting due to lattice softening at/near the hot spots between particles and the resulting formation of bridges between the particles. This mechanism is strongly self-limiting because as soon as the bridges between NPs are formed the longitudinal plasmonic resonance shifts into the IR meaning that such structures no longer absorb the melting light thus inhibiting further melting. Furthermore, in the experiments reported here

the irradiated solutions remain stable for days (the UV/Vis spectra remained unchanged for 48 hours after) after the initial irradiation. This suggests that the capping molecules are not completely destroyed during the melting process.

In summary, we have presented a method to control the morphology of femtosecond laser melting of spherical gold nanoparticle aggregates. This method is based on careful control of both the wavelength and fluence of the melting laser beam. The outcome of the photoinduced melting has been characterised both by spectroscopic and electron microscopy techniques and shows that it is possible to produce larger spherical NPs (400 nm melting), nanorods and nanoprisms (570 nm melting) and larger necklace linked 1D bridged structures (620 - 650 nm melting). The mechanism behind the morphological control is related to the wavelength dependent light concentration of different aggregate geometries. Calculations performed here show that the presence of hot spots can increase the local field by up to two orders of magnitude leading to localised melting of the structures. The calculations also show the spatial distribution and extent of the light concentration is strongly wavelength dependent. In general, this work shows that by careful manipulation of the melting laser wavelength and fluence it is possible to control the outcome of the melting process. If this method can be suitably combined with self assembly of chemically synthesized nanoparticles on surfaces, one can envisage the development of a high-throughput high resolution nanofabrication technique.

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Supporting Information Available

The following files are available free of charge.

Possible supporting information.

- Filename: Full FTAS of the melted solutions??
- more images of the hot spots also for other polarizations??

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Graphical TOC Entry

